

Supplementary Material for Research Paper

“Requirements on Explanations: A Quality Framework for Explainability”

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CONTENTS

I	About	1
II	Literature Study	1
III	Table with References from Literature Study	2
IV	Workshop Structure	4
V	Explanation Design	4
	V-A ER1	4
	V-B ER2	5
	V-C ER3	6
	V-D ER4	7
VI	Case Study	9
	References	12

I. ABOUT

This is the supplementary material for the research paper “Requirements on Explanations: A Quality Framework for Explainability”, accepted at the 30th IEEE International Requirements Engineering 2022 conference. Since the space allocated for research papers did not suffice to elaborate on all research results, we provide the additional information in this document. In particular, we present more details about the literature study – e.g., complete list of analyzed papers and the linking between papers and extracted aspects in our framework – and about the case study. The raw data obtained in this study cannot be shared because of confidentiality agreements.

In the next section (Sec. II), we present the details on the literature study. Sec. III links the aspects of our quality framework to the sources in the literature. In Section IV, we present an overview of the requirements workshop with software engineers, and in Sec. V we provide details about the design of explanations on the software application interface. Finally, in Sec. VI we provide graphics that illustrate the results of our case study.

II. LITERATURE STUDY

The literature study took place in May 2021. To identify external influences on explanations, characteristics of explanations, and forms of evaluating explanations, we performed a literature search in the fields of explainability and human-computer interaction, with focus on relevant aspects for the design of explanations, their presentation on the user interface, and their evaluation. We searched four data bases, namely *ACM Digital Library*, *IEEE Xplore*, *Science Direct*, and *Springer Link*.

The search led to 58 papers that were considered relevant with regard to our research questions. An overview of these papers can be found in the list of references and in Section III, we provide information on which aspects were taken from which papers.

III. TABLE WITH REFERENCES FROM LITERATURE STUDY

In the following tables, we provide links between the aspects of our quality framework to the sources in the literature.

TABLE I: References for Aspects of the Quality Framework

Category	Aspect in the Framework	References
Objectives / Constraints	Objectives	[1]
	Construct	[2]
	Purpose	[1] [3]
	Goals	[4] [5] [6]
	Main Drive	[7]
	Intended Effect	[8]
Business Goals	Stakeholder Goals	[1] [9]
	Higher-level Goals	[1]
	Application Level Goals	[10]
Users' Perception	User Perceived Quality Factors	[1]
	(Consumer) Needs	[11] [12]
	User Goals	[11]
	Intermediate Requirements	[2]
	Human Level	[10]
Explanation Purpose	(Explanation) Purpose	[1]
	Explanatory Goal	[13] [8] [9]
	Function Level	[10]
Context	(Experimental) Context	[14] [12] [15] [2] [16] [17] [5] [18] [9]
	(Explanation) Scope	[3] [19] [18]
	Use Case	[2]
	Stakeholder	[20] [9]
User	(Target / End) User	[21] [22] [23, 24] [9]
	Stakeholder	[14]
	Consumer	[11]
	Explainee	[14, 16]
	Explanation Audience	[10] [9]
Task	Task	[10, 14] [25]
	Activity	[3]
Environment	Environment	[14, 24] [26]
	Application Area / Domain	[10] [26] [24] [9]
Demand	Demand	[14]
Initiative	Manual	[12] [13] [24]
	Automatic	[12] [19] [24] [27] [28]
Timing	Before	[20] [24] [29] [30] [31] [31]
	During	[20] [24] [29]
	After	[20] [24] [29] [30] [31] [26] [31]
Content	User Interface Component(s)	[1] [20]

	Content	[6]
	Granularity	[14] [16]
Information Type	Context	[21] [32] [33] [32] [34] [35] [1] [6]
	Inner Logic	[21] [36] [37] [35] [17] [6] [33]
	Causality	[21] [38] [28] [36] [32] [32] [34] [33] [37] [35] [17] [1][39] [6] [40] [22]
Information	Amount	[6] [41] [42] [43]
Density	Abstraction Level	[37] [42]
Adaptivity	Context-Sensitivity	[22] [33]
	Controllability	[38] [44]
	Personalization	[22] [33] [23] [13] [10]
Presentation	Presentation	[20] [41]
	(Explanation) Type	[6] [20]
Medium	Textual	[10] [8] [13] [36] [19] [19] [38] [33] [9] [1]
	Visual	[10] [36] [45] [38] [1] [46] [9]
	Auditory	[26] [1] [47]
Tone	Factual	[19] [38] [29] [17]
	Emotional	[38] [29] [48] [32] [17]
Grouping	Single	[1] [8] [36] [19] [38]
	Grouped	[1] [8] [13]
Method	Perception Questionnaires	[49], [50] [47] [36] [48] [42] [15] [8]
Qualitative Indicators		
Explanations	Completeness	[49] [51]
	Persuasiveness	[36] [15]
	Usefulness	[36] [15] [8]
	for a comprehensive list	[51]
System	Satisfaction	[8]
	Transparency	[8] [47]
	Trust	[8] [48] [42]
	Scrutability	[8]
Quantitative Metrics	Number of explanation requests	[24] [12] [8]
	User Focus Duration	[8]
	Explanation Exposure Delta	[1]
	Frequency of system use	[52]
	Task performance	[52] [2] [45] [13] [38] [34] [43] [53] [25] [29] [52]
	Learning Rate	[13] [25]
	Task Completion Time	[52]

TABLE II: Most common quality objectives mentioned in the literature

Quality Aspect	References
Trust	[1] [14] [13] [8] [19] [54] [42] [55] [48] [28] [31] [43] [53] [50] [23] [47] [56] [26] [25] [40] [52] [29] [9]
Satisfaction	[1] [14] [13] [8] [57] [54] [49] [43] [53] [50] [11] [5] [56] [6] [25] [40] [52] [15]
Transparency	[1] [14] [13] [12] [8] [21] [54] [42] [50] [58] [23] [47] [56] [52] [53] [11] [44]
Scrutability	[1] [14] [13] [8] [54] [43] [25] [52] [53]
Effectiveness	[1] [14] [13] [8] [54] [34] [42] [53] [58] [52]
Efficiency	[1] [14] [13] [8] [57] [54] [42] [52]
Persuasiveness	[1] [13] [8] [15] [38] [54] [36] [52]

IV. WORKSHOP STRUCTURE

In order to define the goals and requirements for the explanations and to collect initial first implementation ideas, a workshop was held with software engineers, and a customer support expert. By directly applying the developed guideline in the workshop, it was also possible to collect observations on how the framework can be useful. After the initial introduction on explainability, the guide for integrating explanations, and the results from the user feedback analysis, the workshop followed the structure of the framework for explanations. Consequently, information about potential users (Context), then goals (Objectives) and their implementation possibilities (Characteristics), and finally evaluation possibilities were discussed (Evaluation). The overview of the workshop is shown below:

Activity	Description
1. Introduction to Explainability	- Explainability as a NFR - Benefits of explainability in a mobility context - Presentation of the framework - Examples of explanations
2. Presentation of Common Problems	- Common problems found in user feedback - Priorization of problems to be solved
3. Discussion about Personas	- User profiles, contexts
4. Definition of Goals	- Definition of main quality objectives - Concretization of objectives based on the framework
5. Brainstorming about Design Options	- Discussion about aspects of explanations - Aspects of interface design
6. Definition of Metrics	- Discussion about metrics and their feasibility - Definition of evaluation strategy

TABLE III: Workshop Structure

V. EXPLANATION DESIGN

In this section, we present more details on the design of each explanation requirement (ER). The design took place in July 2021, after the workshop. During this period, mock-ups were designed and discussed in a daily basis with the team. We go over the design of the explanations in greater detail and show screenshots of the final design in the app.

A. *ERI*

The collaborative routing algorithm works by calculating each route depending on the routes of other users. To shed more light on this logic, the explanation of the routing algorithm has been implemented in two different levels of granularity. First, end-users could click on an icon with the number of users that would influence the routing. By clicking on it, a small window on the bottom of the screen appeared, containing a short explanation, a “close” button, and a “learn more” button. In a first

version, the explanation was “In the last 15 minutes, we have collected anonymous traffic data from [number of users] users in your area.”. However, this sentence was found to be too technical for the end-users during discussions with stakeholders in the company. Therefore, we rephrased it to “The routes of [number of users] users in your area are included in the calculation of your route”, to make the relevance of this information to the users become more clear. As a further explanation option, end users could click on “learn more” to jump to the corresponding Help Center article that would explain the details of the collaborative routing algorithm. A link from the app directly to the help center did not exist in the application before this work.

(a)

Fig. 1: Final design for ER1

B. ER2

On the map, which is the main interaction element of the software application, closures, road works were already traffic jams signalized. According to user feedback, this contextual information was not sufficiently understandable. Therefore, a new Help Center article was created as part of this work on this topic. This article is suitable for users who are using the application for the first time. This article was also made accessible before navigation start. To avoid cluttering the default map view with multiple ways to access help center articles, the ability to get to this explanation was integrated into the route preview. During route preview, a button with the question “How was my route calculated?” was provided at the top of the window. By clicking on it, the user would be redirected to the corresponding article. Several prototypes were created for this as well, with the final decision being made to ensure that the button did not take up too much space.

Fig. 2: Final design for ER2

C. ER3

The goal of this explanation was to explain possible reasons for what, from an end-user' perspective, could be considered as a “weird” route. The chosen approach to explain this was to display traffic events on the current route. This context information should help to understand why the application recommends unusual routes. However, this is not trivial, since the calculation of the traffic volume and its subjective perception of the end user is not clear. Another problem is that it was a technical challenge to define which route would be subjectively perceived as “normal” to each end-user on the same route. Therefore, the chosen solution was to calculate the ratio of average route duration and use it as baseline for comparison. The data is then mapped to “low traffic”, “moderate traffic”, and “high traffic” levels. There is also a “normal” traffic situation where no explanation is shown to the end users. The threshold values were determined internally through test drives. End-users could obtain the information in three ways. First, the information was displayed in the route preview, together with the information about the route duration. The total travel time for the route was displayed in green (low traffic), standard text color (normal traffic), orange (moderate traffic) and red (heavy traffic). Since it was noticed in the first prototype that the colors alone were not meaningful, a short explanatory text was added. In addition, throughout the navigation, the arrival time and the travel time are displayed in the appropriate color and also updated as the traffic situation changes. During navigation, information about traffic volume was provided via synthesized speech as shown in Table IV. The tone of these voice prompts was somewhat emotional to create sympathy.

(a)

Fig. 3: Final design for ER3

Traffic Volume	Voice Prompt
low	Today the roads are clear. You will reach your destination <destination name> at <time>.
normal	You will reach your destination <destination name> at <time>.
moderate	Since today is a bit busier, you will reach your destination <destination name> at <time>.
high	Since today is very busy, you will reach your destination <destination name> at <time>.

TABLE IV: Voice prompts at the beginning of navigation dependent on the traffic volume

D. ER4

The last statement developed concerns the scrutability aspect. The goal is to indicate to end users when they cannot currently rely on the position on the route. This is the case in tunnels, for example, and is especially critical when a turn command is about to be issued and thus comes in the wrong place. A new algorithm has been integrated within the navigation app to decide when the GPS is inaccurate. In this case, not only the accuracy (determined by the GPS module) was considered, but also the time of the last GPS update. As design in the first draft only an icon containing the text “Innaccurate position” with a

voice-over with the same information. Since voice overs are often deactivated by the end-user, the visibility of the explanation during test drives turned out to be insufficient. Therefore, in the final design, we changed the position of the explanation and added a circle on the map to indicate the accuracy range.

Fig. 4: Final design for ER4

Topic	Questions
Collaborative Routing	What is collaborative routing / how does it work? Why do I need a permanent internet connection? Why are no standard routes displayed?
Navigation	Why is this route / detour taken? Why are the routes with this app longer? Why is the position inaccurate?
Trust in the system	Where does the traffic / road closure data come from? What is happening with my data? Why do I need location services when starting the app? How can I know if this route was well calculated?
Features	What does the coloring of the route show? How do I report a road closure? How do I enter my destination? How do I create favorites?

TABLE V: User Questions derived from reviews in the app stores and frequently used help center articles.

Fig. 5: Route Satisfaction represented by star ratings

VI. CASE STUDY

In this section, we present additional data from our case study. The case study took place in August 2021, during two weeks. Table V shows the most important user questions that we derived from analyzing reviews in the app stores and the most frequently accessed help center articles. These represent usability issues that could be solved by explainability. The three questions that were prioritized in the workshop are highlighted in bold.

In our quantitative analysis, we used the interactive format of our static explanations (ER1 and ER2) to get additional data as already described in the paper. Here, we additionally show in Figure 5 how the star ratings for the calculated routes differed between groups.

The results of our qualitative evaluation are depicted in Figure 6 and Figure 7. Figure 6 shows the ratings on statements concerning the demand for explanations and Figure 7 the ratings concerning the content of explanations.

(a) ER1: collaborative routing

(b) ER2: collaborative algorithm

(c) ER3: traffic volume

(d) ER4: position accuracy

Fig. 6: Results of the Qualitative Study for the Explanation Demand

(a) ER1: collaborative routing

(b) ER2: collaborative algorithm

(c) ER3: traffic volume

(d) ER4: position accuracy

Fig. 7: Results of the Qualitative Study for the Explanation Content

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